

Team name: _____

Recipe number: [_]

Category of uncertainty

- Ignorance
- Credibility
- Imprecision
- Incompletedness

Locus

Name

- Very high
- High
- Medium
- Low
- Very Low

Target

Asserted value

Certainty

Description

- Date
- Object
- PlaceName
- ProductionMethod
- Event
- ObjectName
- Country
- Location
- Org
- Time
- Geolocation
- Person
- Ingredient
- Occupation
- Place
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